

Population Burst Propagation Across Interacting Areas of the Brain: Supporting Information

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We provide supplementary information and analyses in the form of appendices, figures, and
tables. The details of the drifting gratings conditions used in our analysis, such as temporal
frequency and orientation, are summarized in Table S1. Details about the simulation study
are in section SS1, Table S3, Table S4, and Table S5. Supplementary analyses about curve
fitting are in SS2, additional material about the priors is in section SS3, and essential formulas
for partial correlation and regression are in section SS4. Selected regression results are in
Table S2. More supplementary figures are in section SS5.

The remainder of our supplementary material is in a series of figures. The complete set of
correlations, that is posterior distributions of the correlations, are in Figure S3 with corre-
sponding full partial correlations in Figure S4 (full here means after conditioning on all the
rest of the features). The plot of marginal and partial correlation similar to Figure 6B,D for
the case of V1 and LM conditioning on AL is shown in Figure S5. Estimated Peak-2 timing
of V1 and LM using the GPFA method (Yu et al. 2009) is shown in Figure S6. The highly
concentrated posterior distributions of p_{ac} are displayed in Figure S7. The complete set of
estimated templates, similar to the plots for selected conditions, are in Figure S8. Different
plots for the same estimated templates are in Figure S9, while Figure S10 shows additional
comparisons of the templates to the corresponding PSTHs obtained from the same selected
set of neurons. The locations of recorded neurons, together with their classification (based
on the posterior median), are shown in Figure S11. Goodness-of-fit results are in Figures
S14, S15, S16, and S18. Simulated neural activities involving different template shapes and

the consequence of template matching are shown in Figure S19.

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S1 Simulation study

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The true model in the simulations together with the spiking data were generated according to the process in Equation (1)-(8). The matrix Σ^{pop} and the average population activities $f_{a,c}^{\text{pop}}$, $f_{a,c}^{\text{local-1}}$, $f_{a,c}^{\text{local-2}}$ came from the fit to the real data. We included 3 features (Gain, Peak-1, Peak-2) for 3 virtual brain areas. The total number of trials was 180. For one simulation dataset, we totally drew 2000 MCMC samples, and dropped first 500 samples. The parameters were initialized with the true values. We totally created 500 repetitions which could make the CI coverage have a standard error around $\sqrt{0.95 \times 0.05/500} \approx 0.01$ with 95% CI. We calculate the CI ends standard error by following (Doss et al. 2014, sec. 3.2.1). A loose lower bound of RMSE can be determined by the standard error of Pearson’s correlation with the same sample size, while assuming there is no bias and the true feature values are known. The standard error monotonically decreases as correlation absolute value grows. The standard error of Pearson’s correlation is between 0.012 (if correlation is 0.9) and 0.072 (if correlation is 0) (Fisher 1915). The RMSE range of the simulation is slightly larger than this range due to extra uncertainty from other parts of the model and the bias of the estimation.

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Our model assumes the neurons within each group have the same property, meaning they share the same intensity functions $f_{a,c}^{\text{pop}}$, $f_{a,c}^{\text{local-1}}$, $f_{a,c}^{\text{local-2}}$. To verify this assumption, we created two extra simulation scenarios by adding neuron-to-neuron variance to the intensity functions. We did not find systematic error in the curve fitting on the real data, so the injected noise was not specified in specific ways. Instead, we leveraged the generative model and created the noise learned from the data. In one case, we added mild neuron-to-neuron variance. We first collected posterior samples of f^{pop} , $f^{\text{local-1}}$, $f^{\text{local-2}}$. Then we randomly assigned a sample to each neuron with respect to its group. In the other case, we added more aggressive neuron-to-neuron variance. We approximated the conditional posterior distribution (Equation (10) and (11)) of the intensity function coefficients using Laplacian method when the sampling was mixed. This output a multivariate Normal distribution, where the mean was the MAP, and the covariance matrix was the inverse of the Hessian. Next we amplified the covariance matrix by 20 times, and drew samples for each neuron. We replicated the evaluations for these two extra experiments, and the results are similar.

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For the mild noise case, the bias values of the estimated correlations are in the range $[-0.039, 0.05]$ (the mean of all pairs of features is 0.0025). The correlation posterior CI coverage is shown in Table S4. The RMSE values are in range $[0.025, 0.091]$ (the mean of all pairs of features is 0.074). The simulation standard errors of CI end points were small relative to the RMSE values. The range is in $[0.001, 0.010]$ (the mean of all pairs of features is 0.0057). For the aggressive noise case, the bias values of the estimated correlations are in the range $[-0.033, 0.047]$ (the mean of all pairs of features is 0.001). The correlation posterior CI coverage is shown in Table S5. The RMSE values are in range $[0.024, 0.088]$ (the mean of all pairs of features is 0.072). The simulation standard errors of CI end points were small relative to the RMSE values. The range is in $[0.001, 0.0092]$ (the mean of all pairs of features is 0.0056).

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Figure S1: **Comparison of different curve fitting methods.** For each of 4 methods, the data has 150 trials. For spline fitting the knots are shown at the bottom of the figure. The method we used, labeled Bayesian smoothing spline, chooses the tuning parameter using 5-fold cross-validation. For BARS we used the default parameters.

Figure 1 shows a simulation example with two peaks similar to the “pop” activity. We compare the penalized spline method we applied (labeled Bayesian smoothing spline) with two other methods, BARS (Kass, Eden, and Brown 2014, sec. 15.2.6) and spline fitting with manually selected knots (sec. 15.2.4). Our method has 100 knots and 102 basis elements. The regression spline model with manually chosen knots has 16 knots, 18 basis elements. BARS does not have a fixed number of knots. We used the default parameters in the online package (Kelly 2020). The estimated curves are all very close the true model, and the pointwise CI bands trap the true curve very well. The synthesized data has 150 trials. The CI band of the spline fitting (top right plot) is calculated from standard formulas (using the Fisher information matrix). The positions of the knots are shown at the bottom. The tuning parameter of our method (bottom left plot) comes from 5-fold cross-validation (Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman 2009, sec. 7.10.1). The spline fit model has 18 free parameters, so the number of degrees of freedom is 18. The BARS MCMC samples on average used 10.3 knots, so the average number of degrees of freedom is 12.3. For the Bayesian smoothing spline method, the number of effective degrees of freedom is 6.6; this is obtained by maximizing the posterior and approximating the problem as least squares (in the Reinsch form) (Demmler and Reinsch 1975). As with smoothing splines, even though the number of knots is large, the effective number of parameters is small (Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman 2009, sec. 5.4.1).

The method needs the hyperparameter η to control the smoothness of the curves. In the real data analysis, we first selected a good initial tuning parameter (the tuning procedure can be run in a few iterations to have a good initial guess, or use simulated data), fitted the model and fixed other parameters except for the curve fitting coefficients. Then we trained the curve fitting by maximizing a posterior (MAP), which is equivalent to penalized maximizing

the likelihood or the Tikhonov regression. We selected the tuning parameter using 5-fold cross-validation by splitting the trials into 5 segments in all conditions (Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman 2009, sec. 10.7.1) while holding the neuron clustering when the algorithm is mixed. We also tested the tuning parameter on simulated data with two-peak patterns, the result was the same. Since the number of neurons or trials used to estimate the curve varies, we multiply η with the number of trials in Equation (16), and (17) (assuming the trial length is fixed, otherwise the trial length can also be a factor), so that the tuning parameter selection is invariant of or less sensitive to sample size.

S3 Priors

We first list some properties of inverse-Wishart distribution, which will later be used for designing the prior for Σ^{pop} . The following properties can be derived from the conclusions in (Barnard, McCulloch, and Meng 2000; Huang, Wand, et al. 2013). Consider the following distribution for the $D \times D$ covariance matrix Σ . The scale matrix Ψ is diagonal with all positive values. The number of the degrees of freedom is ν .

$$\Sigma \sim \text{inverse-Wishart}(\Psi, \nu) \quad (12)$$

The marginal distribution of any correlation entry is the following,

$$\rho = \frac{\Sigma_{i,j}}{\sqrt{\Sigma_{i,i}\Sigma_{j,j}}}, \quad i \neq j$$

$$p(\rho) = \frac{1}{2} \text{Beta} \left(\frac{\rho+1}{2} \middle| \frac{\nu-D+1}{2}, \frac{\nu-D+1}{2} \right), \quad \rho \in [-1, 1] \quad (13)$$

If $\nu = D + 1$, the marginal distribution is uniform. Σ has mode $\Psi/4$, the mean does not exist.

For any partial correlation entry,

$$\rho' = -\frac{\Omega_{i,j}}{\sqrt{\Omega_{i,i}\Omega_{j,j}}}, \quad \Omega = \Sigma^{-1}, \quad i \neq j$$

$$\rho' \sim \frac{1}{2} \text{Beta} \left(\frac{\rho'+1}{2} \middle| \frac{\nu-1}{2}, \frac{\nu-1}{2} \right), \quad \rho' \in [-1, 1] \quad (14)$$

If $\nu = D + 1$, the marginal distribution is a zero-concentrated distribution. As the dimension D increases, it becomes more concentrated. Marginal and partial correlation properties above do not depend on the scale matrix as long as all diagonal elements are positive.

Next, consider the marginal distribution of the diagonal element $\Sigma_{i,i}$,

$$\Sigma_{i,i} \sim \text{Inverse-Gamma} \left(\frac{\nu-D+1}{2}, \frac{\Psi_{i,i}}{2} \right) \quad (15)$$

The inverse-Gamma distribution is diffuse enough to capture the uncertainty using its long thick tail as shown in Figure 2. If select $\nu = D + 1$, the marginal distribution does not depend on D . Some previous works, such as (Alvarez, Niemi, and Simpson 2014), add extra uncertainty for $\Psi_{i,i}$ in the prior, but we think it is not necessary.

Figure S2: **An example of variance $\Sigma_{i,i}$ marginal distribution.** $\Psi_{i,i} = 4$. The mode is 1, the corresponding quantile percentage is 13.5%. The median is at 2.89. The quantile at 2 corresponds to 36.8%, which stays between the mode and the median. The 70.0% quantile is 5.61 times of the mode. Note that the ratio between these quantiles is invariant of Ψ and D .

In Equation (8), $\Psi_0 = 2\Phi_0$ is a diagonal scale matrix. The number of the degrees of freedom 106
is $\nu_0 = D + 1$, where $D = d \cdot A$ is the dimension of the matrix Σ^{pop} (Equation (7)). Based 107
on the properties above, such a design leads to some desired properties: 1, as detailed prior 108
knowledge for the correlation between features is limited, we use uninformative prior for cor- 109
relations (Barnard, McCulloch, and Meng 2000). The marginal distribution of a correlation 110
derived from Σ^{pop} is uniform on $[-1, 1]$ (see Equation (13)); 2, the marginal distribution of 111
partial correlations derived from Σ^{pop} concentrate at 0. More specifically, it is the scaled Beta 112
distribution on $[-1, 1]$ with coefficients $(D/2, D/2)$ (see Equation (14)). As the dimension 113
 D grows, it concentrates more at the center. Conditioning on more relevant or correlated 114
features is more likely to make the partial correlation closer to zero; 3, the marginal variance 115
of a feature i is diffused with inverse-Gamma($1, [\Phi_0]_{ii}$) (see Equation (15)). Φ_0 is a diagonal 116
covariance matrix with the standard deviations being the ranges of the features. The ranges 117
of Peak-1, Peak-2 and Gain are roughly estimated using a different animal. The standard 118
deviations for the Gain, Peak-1 shifting and Peak-2 shifting are 0.15 log spikes/sec, 10 ms, 119
30 ms. We set $\Psi_0 = 2\Phi_0$ such that $[\Phi_0]_{i,i}$ is on the long tail in the distribution in Equation 120
(15) and it stays between the mode and the median (also see the above figure). This can 121
make the prior of the feature variance less informative. 122

The prior for the neurons' memberships uses Dirichlet distribution Equation (9) for its sim- 123
plicity. The hyperparameter is $\alpha = 5 \cdot \mathbf{1}$ as an uninformative prior which is relatively small 124
comparing to the number of neurons. The membership assignment is insensitive to α in a 125
certain range. We checked the results with $\alpha = \mathbf{1}$ (flat prior) and $\alpha = 10 \cdot \mathbf{1}$. Then, we 126
quantified the distinction using the difference ratio of memberships' modes of all neurons in 127
all conditions. The total count is $N \cdot C$. The model with $\alpha = 5 \cdot \mathbf{1}$ and the model with 128
 $\alpha = \mathbf{1}$ have 2.1% membership difference. The model with $\alpha = 5 \cdot \mathbf{1}$ and the model with 129
 $\alpha = 10 \cdot \mathbf{1}$ have 1.4% membership difference. In addition, the prior with $\alpha = 5$ plays a role 130
of regularization, which prevents the model from an empty clusters before the samples get 131
mixed, while $\alpha = 1$ does not do so. 132

The priors related to curve fitting are the following,

$$\beta_{a,c}^{\text{pop}} \mid \eta, \Omega \sim \frac{1}{\tilde{Z}_0} \exp\{-\eta N_{\text{pop},a,c} R_c (\beta_{a,c}^{\text{pop}})^T \Omega \beta_{a,c}^{\text{pop}}\} \quad (16)$$

$$\beta_{a,c}^{\text{local-1}} \mid \eta, \Omega \sim \frac{1}{\tilde{Z}_1} \exp\{-\eta N_{\text{local-1},a,c} R_c (\beta_{a,c}^{\text{local-1}})^T \Omega \beta_{a,c}^{\text{local-1}}\} \quad (17)$$

$$p(\beta_{a,c}^{\text{local-2}}) \propto 1 \quad (18)$$

\tilde{Z}_0, \tilde{Z}_1 are the normalizers of the distributions. The constraint of the coefficients is designed for smoothness in the same spirit as the smoothing spline (Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman 2009, sec. 5.4). In Gibbs sampling, the penalty becomes the log prior density, where the prior is normal. The smoothing parameter η is tuned using cross-validation. Details are discussed in section SS2. $N_{\text{pop},a,c}$ and $N_{\text{local-1},a,c}$ count the number of neurons in group “pop” and “local-1” respectively. R_c is the number of trials of a condition. Multiplying with N and R makes η less sensitive to varying sample size.

S4 Properties of multivariate Normal distribution

We derive the marginal correlation, partial correlation and R^2 values directly from estimated covariance matrix. Let X be a random vector following multivariate Normal distribution $X \sim N(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \Sigma)$. Σ is the covariance matrix. The marginal correlation between two entries X_i, X_j is,

$$\rho(X_i, X_j) = \frac{\Sigma_{i,j}}{\sqrt{\Sigma_{i,i} \cdot \Sigma_{j,j}}}$$

The partial correlation is derived from the marginal and conditional distribution. Let us consider the conditional distribution of $X_W \mid X_Z$, where X_W, X_Z are entries of X . $A = W \cup Z$ is the index set of those entries. Then,

$$(X_W, X_Z)^T \sim N(\boldsymbol{\mu}_A, \Sigma_{A,A})$$

The conditional distribution follows,

$$X_W \mid X_Z \sim N(\mu_{W \mid Z}, \Sigma_{W \mid Z})$$

$\mu_{W \mid Z} = \mu_W + \Sigma_{W,Z} \Sigma_{Z,Z}^{-1} (X_Z - \mu_Z)$, $\Sigma_{W \mid Z} = \Sigma_{W,W} - \Sigma_{W,Z} \Sigma_{Z,Z}^{-1} \Sigma_{Z,W}$. Then we can get the partial correlation using the covariance matrix $\Sigma_{W \mid Z}$. Now set $W = \{i, j\}$. $\Sigma' = \Sigma_{W \mid Z}$.

$$\rho(X_i, X_j \mid X_Z) = \frac{\Sigma'_{i,j}}{\sqrt{\Sigma'_{i,i} \cdot \Sigma'_{j,j}}}$$

The regression analysis is also based on the conditional distribution. Let $y = X_W$ be the independent variable, W has a single index. The conditional relation can be rewritten as,

$$y = X_Z \beta + b + \varepsilon$$

where $\beta = \Sigma_{Z,Z}^{-1} \Sigma_{Z,W}$, $b = \mu_W - \Sigma_{W,Z} \Sigma_{Z,Z}^{-1} \mu_Z$, $\varepsilon \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma_{W \mid Z})$. So we can derive

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\Sigma_{W \mid Z}}{\Sigma_{W,W}}$$

$\Sigma_{W,W}$ is the variance of the independent variable, $\Sigma_{W \mid Z}$ is the variance of the regression residual.

S5 Supplementary figures and tables

Figure S3: **Full marginal correlations** Pairwise marginal correlations between all features. Significantly positive values are labeled by red, and significantly negative ones are labeled by blue.

Figure S4: **Full partial correlations** Each entry shows the correlation between two features conditioning on all the rest. Considering all combinations of variables there are 4572 partial correlations among the 9 features. Here we display the 45 correlations together with the 45 corresponding full conditional partial correlations and we also provide several additional partial correlations. Significantly positive values are labeled by red, and significantly negative ones are labeled by blue.

Figure S5: Marginal correlation and partial correlations of peak timing This figure is similar to Figure 6, except that panels A and B involve V1 Peak-2 and LM Peak-2 and panels C and D involve Peak-1. **A** shows the estimated marginal correlation. Each dot represents the estimated time of Peak-2 on a given trial, based on the posterior median. **B** shows the estimated partial correlation after conditioning on AL Peak-2. Each dot represents the residual from a regression on the conditioning variable (the correlation of these residuals being the partial correlation given the conditioning variable). The embedded plots in the corner are the posterior distributions of the correlations. The number in the embedded plot is the mode of the posterior. In comparison to Figure 6, with conditioning on LM Peak-2, there is not such a dramatic reduction of the correlation of V1 and LM Peak-2 timing after conditioning on AL Peak-2 timing. **C**, **D**, **E**, **F**, **G** and **H** display results similar to those in A and B but for Peak-1. The pairs of V1 Peak-1 and AL Peak-1, V1 Peak-1 and LM Peak-1, and LM Peak-1 and AL Peak-1 have significant correlations, but after conditioning on the Peak-1 of the third region their correlations are not reduced to zero or a small value. Especially, after conditioning on LM Peak-1 the reduction of correlation between V1 Peak-1 and AL Peak-1 appears less dramatic than that of Peak-2 (as shown in Figure 6D, and it is more clearly less dramatic in the second mouse).

Figure S6: **Peak-2 timing of V1 and LM from GPFA.** Similar to Figure 1, the goal is to extract peak times from all trials based on population activity. The method includes all neurons. The time bin width is 2 ms, and the dimension is 3. For one region, one condition and one trial, we first stacked all spike trains from all neurons, then fed these into the GPFA software (<https://elephant.readthedocs.io/en/latest/tutorials/gpfa.html>). The GPFA returned low dimensional factors. We used the first component as the fitted smoothed curve. The algorithm was initialized with PCA, so the first component carried the main variance and it captured the two-peak pattern consistently. We searched for the peak-2 maximum between 150 ms and 350 ms. We repeated this procedure for all areas, all conditions, and all trials.

Figure S7: **The posterior distributions of $p_{a,c}$.** Each condition has a group of 3 triangles for V1, LM and AL. $p_{a,c}$ is a 3-entry vector showing the probability of the subgroup memberships. So $p_{a,c}$ are in 2-simplex and they are mapped to the triangles. The left angle represents the “pop”, the right one is the local-1, and the top one is “local-2”. If a point is closer to an angle meaning the corresponding component has a larger portion. To simplify the visualization, we approximate the posterior using bivariate Normal distribution. The dot is the mean, and the ellipse is the 95% credible region of the Normal distribution. Most distributions are far from “pop” corner (left angle), which means “pop” takes small portion of neurons. The distributions are close to “local-2” corner (top angle), so “local-2” include a large part of neuron. All the distributions are highly centralized, meaning the uncertainty for neuron clustering is very small. The portions slightly vary from condition to condition, which shows the diversity of neurons’ behavior.

Figure S8: **Population templates in all conditions.** Similar to Figure 7, the figure shows the fitted population templates with the median and the pointwise 95% CI of the posterior. The figure is composed of 3×3 blocks for 13 conditions. In a condition block, the columns are $\exp\{f_{a,c}^{\text{pop}}\}$, $\exp\{f_{a,c}^{\text{local-1}}\}$, and $\exp\{f_{a,c}^{\text{local-2}}\}$. The rows are V1, LM, and AL.

Figure S9: **Population templates in all conditions.** The curves are the same as those in Figure S8, which are the medians of the $\exp\{f_{a,c}^{\text{pop}}\}$ and $\exp\{f_{a,c}^{\text{local-1}}\}$. Each curve represents one condition. We overlap the curve across conditions to demonstrate the condition-to-condition variance, which is equivalent or larger than the feature variance, such as Peak-1 or Peak-2 shifting. This suggests disaggregating the data to better capture the subtly varied features.

Figure S10: **Examples of $\exp\{f_{a,c}^{\text{pop}}\}$ versus PSTH.** The PSTH and the pointwise CI are estimated using Bayesian smoothing spline similar to Algorithm 1 line 5 without incorporating peaks shifts. The PSTH curves fit the same set of neurons as in the “pop” group (selected from the mode of the posterior). In many conditions, the Peak-2 of $\exp\{f_{a,c}^{\text{pop}}\}$ becomes narrower and higher than the PSTH. The CI bands around the Peak-2 hardly overlap, for example `stimulus_condition_id = 249, 268, 280`. This is because the activity trials are aligned better. However, in some conditions like 261 AL, Peak-2 of the model is not significantly higher than the PSTH. In most conditions, Peak-1 of $\exp\{f_{a,c}^{\text{pop}}\}$ does not change much because the trial-to-trial deviations are small. Another observation is that the variability of Peak-2 shapes is larger than that of Peak-1. This explains why Peak-2 in Figure 1, the overall average, is wider and lower than Peak-2 in the template: there is trial-to-trial temporal blurring together with condition-to-condition variability. This also suggests that averaging neural activity, even with more trials, may not get more accurate neural responses without considering the time-shifting deviations or without treating different conditions separately.

Figure S11: **The location of recorded neurons.** The figure shows the memberships and the locations of the neurons in every area (by column) and every condition (by row). The x and y axes label the relative positions of the electrodes, with depth along the x axis, relative to the most superficial unit. The membership is determined by the posterior median. The dot shape or color represent its membership. More precisely, the location of the neuron is the location of the channel that records the neuron signal. One channel can record the signal from more than one neuron.

Figure S12: **Peak-2 timing: correlation and partial correlation across regions for second mouse.** The analysis is similar to Figure 6 but uses data from the mouse of session 757216464. Panels A,B display correlations, with each dot representing the estimated time of peak-2 on a given trial. Panels C,D display estimated partial correlations, with each dot representing the residual from a regression on the conditioning variable (the correlation of these residuals being the partial correlation given the conditioning variable). Panels C,D contain partial correlation results, with the areas in C corresponding to those in A and the areas in D corresponding to those in B. All panels use posterior medians as estimates. **A** Despite large variability in peak-2 timing the correlation of LM peak2 time and AL peak-2 time is close to 1. The plot embedded in the upper left corner displays the posterior distribution of the correlation. For the inset, the posterior median and 95% CI (.025 and .975 posterior quantiles) are .81 (.66,.85). **B** This plot is for areas V1 and AL, analogous to that in panel A. Inset median and CI: .60 (.49,.70). **C** The residual Peak-2 times for LM and AL are plotted, after regressing on the Peak-2 time of V1 timing. Inset median and CI: .60 (.36,.76). **D** The residual Peak-2 times for V1 and AL are plotted, after regressing on the Peak-2 time of LM. The partial correlation in panel C is somewhat smaller, but not dramatically smaller, than the correlation in panel A. In contrast, the partial correlation in panel D is close to zero, and very much different than the large correlation in panel B. Inset median CI: .01 (-.25,.30).

Figure S13: Distributions, across trials, of peak timing and of time lags between areas for second mouse. Again, the data are from session 757216464. Histograms of the estimated peak times and time lags are shown together with median and .025 and .975 quantiles. The histogram in part A was formed from the collection (across trials) of Peak-1 times estimated for each trial, and the other histograms were created similarly. The results are very similar to those for the first mouse, except the Peak-1 times in area AL were earlier for the second mouse than for the first. **A** The histogram of estimated Peak-1 times for V1 is centered at 55 ms post stimulus onset with 95% of values falling in the range (46,82) ms; for LM and AL the corresponding times are 66 (58,90) ms and 60 (54,80) ms (for the first mouse the AL Peak-1 times were 70 (64,86) ms). **B** The histograms show that V1 leads LM by 10 ms with 95% of trials having lead times in the range (8.6, 12.5) ms; V1 leads AL by 4.4 (2.7, 5.9) ms; and AL leads LM by 5.6 (4.4, 8.2) ms (for the first mouse the Peak-1 times in AL and LM were nearly simultaneous). **C** Histograms of estimated Peak-2 times show that Peak-2 times are much more variable than Peak-1 times. For V1 the Peak-2 times are centered at 236 ms with 95% of trials having times in the range (152,304) ms; for LM and AL the values are 246 (158,315) ms and 242 (156,302) ms. **D** The Peak-2 time lags between areas are much more precise than the times themselves, and lags are much smaller than those for Peak-1: V1 leads LM by 9.3 ms with 95% of trials falling in the range (7.6, 11.8) ms; V1 leads AL by 5.3 (3.5, 8.0) ms; AL leads LM by 3.9 (1.2, 6.4) ms.

Figure S14: **Population PSTH and fitted activities.** The figure presents results for the “pop” neurons, which are the neurons involved in interaction across areas. The gray histogram shows the PSTH of the raw data. The time bin width is 2 ms. For each condition c and area a , we stack 15 trials from all $N_{a,c}$ pop neurons, yielding $15N_{a,c}$ spike trains merged in the PSTH. The fitted model is presented in dark curves. For each condition, there will be 15 fitted population intensity functions (posterior mean of $\lambda_{g,a,r,c}$, $g = \text{pop}$ as in Eq (1)). The dark curve is the average of those 15 intensity functions.

Figure S15: **Model predictions of spike count correlations.** Model fits (dark curves) are overlaid on histograms of spike count correlations. **A** The first row shows the histogram of spike count correlations of all pairs of neurons. **B, C, D** The second row shows the histograms of neurons within an area indicated by the label above the plot. **E, F, G** The last row shows the histograms of neurons between areas indicated by the label above the plot. Model fits were obtained by assuming each neuron’s intensity was exactly equal to the population intensity given by the fitted model, as in Eq (1). Spikes were generated according to its intensity, and spike count correlations were calculated in the same way as the raw data, and the histogram was mildly smoothed. This was repeated 10 times and the 10 curves were averaged to get the dark curves shown in the plots. Even though this check involves behavior of *individual* neurons, rather than population behavior (the fits assume all neurons have the same intensity, which the model does not assume), still, the model fits the data well. Mild lack of fit is visible in some cases.

Figure S16: Model predictions of population spike train cross-correlation. The figure shows Pearson (normalized) cross-correlation functions between pairs of population spike trains, based on interacting population (“pop”) neurons. Spike trains were first smoothed with a Gaussian filter having bandwidth (standard deviation parameter) 20 ms. To evaluate the model, the population spike trains are generated from fitted intensity function. In each case, the data based cross-correlation is in gray and the model prediction is black. The model-based version is based on spike trains simulated from fitted intensities, with the simulation run 10 times and the results averaged to get the plotted curve. The title of each subplot indicates the direction of the positive lag on the x -axis. For example, in **A**, The correlation on the positive lag side is larger than the negative lag side, meaning V1’s activity occurs earlier than that in AL. The model provides reasonably good fits, capturing lead-lag timing according to these correlation curves.

Figure S18: **Goodness-of-fit test.** KS test for “pop” group of all three regions (shown by checker boards), all conditions (shown by rows), and all trials (shown by columns). The dotted lines are 99% CI of KS test. At the bottom of the figure, we show some examples of good fits (highlighted by green in the grid) and bad fits (highlighted by red in the grid). Some trials may have unexpected activities that are different from the templates ($f_{a,c}^{\text{POP}}$), but the method is still able to find Peak-1 and Peak-2 positions. Because activity is modeled by matching the template, it may lose some details of each trial and fail some goodness-of-fit tests, but it can accurately capture the main features of interest. For example, the plot of V1 condition 268 trial 8 has a bump at the end of the trial, which is not common in other trials of the same condition. The example of V1 268 trial 0 is a representative trial of the condition, which matches the template very well.

Figure S19: **Time-warping and template matching with different population activity profiles.** Four scenarios were assessed: **A** has a single relatively sharp peak, like those in our data, while **B** has a much broader peak (so it could become more difficult to locate the maximum); **C** is inverted, so that the problem is to find the minimum; **D** has neither a true maximum nor a minimum and, instead, the center of the template is defined to be half way up to the asymptotic maximal firing rate. The first row shows simulated spikes using the templates in the second row. The second row presents examples of templates with different shapes. The vertical line indicates the landmark position. The third row shows the template matching score (judged by log-likelihood) as a function of landmark position. The best match is indicated by the maximum score, which is expected to be at the true landmark position (vertical gray line). All these examples have the same number of trials. For all template shapes, the template matching method is able to accurately identify the true landmark position.

Condition id	249	256	257	260	261	268	270	274	275	278	280	281	284
Temporal frequency [Hz]	8	15	8	4	8	4	8	4	8	8	8	15	15
Orientation [deg]	90	270	315	315	135	45	45	90	0	225	270	315	45
Spatial frequency [cycles/deg]	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Contrast [%]	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80

Table S1: **Stimulus conditions** Parameters for 13 trials in session 798911424 used for our analysis. The visual stimulus is drifting gratings. The parameters of a condition include temporal frequency (Hz), orientation (deg), spatial frequency (cycles/deg), and contrast (percentage). The spatial frequency and contrast are the same for all conditions.

Model	Y	X	R^2	Difference	R^2
A0	AL-P2	V1-P2	0.71 (0.60,0.82)	A2 - A0	0.12 (0.06,0.19)
A1	AL-P2	V1-P1,LM-P1,AL-P1	0.34 (0.14,0.53)	A2 - A1	0.50 (0.35,0.64)
A2	AL-P2	V1-P1,LM-P1,AL-P1,V1-P2	0.85 (0.75,0.89)	A3 - A1	0.58 (0.41,0.72)
A3	AL-P2	V1-P1,LM-P1,AL-P1,LM-P2	0.92 (0.85,0.95)	A3 - A2	0.07 (0.04,0.14)
A4	AL-P2	V1-P1,LM-P1,AL-P1,V1-P2, LM-P2	0.92 (0.85,0.95)	A4 - A2	0.08 (0.05,0.14)
				A4 - A3	0.01 (0.00,0.01)

Model	Y	X	R^2	Difference	R^2
B0	LM-P2	V1-P2	0.79 (0.72,0.84)	B2 - B0	0.07 (0.03,0.14)
B1	LM-P2	V1-P1,LM-P1,AL-P1	0.32 (0.09,0.54)	B2 - B1	0.57 (0.34,0.75)
B2	LM-P2	V1-P1,LM-P1,AL-P1,V1-P2	0.87 (0.79,0.91)	B3 - B1	0.61 (0.40,0.78)
B3	LM-P2	V1-P1,LM-P1,AL-P1,LM-P2	0.92 (0.84,0.95)	B3 - B2	0.05 (0.00,0.10)
B4	LM-P2	V1-P1,LM-P1,AL-P1,V1-P2, LM-P2	0.94 (0.89,0.96)	B4 - B2	0.07 (0.04,0.12)
				B4 - B3	0.02 (0.00,0.05)

Model	Y	X	R^2	Difference	R^2
C0	V1-G	LM-G	0.62 (0.54,0.69)	C0 - C1	0.28 (0.18,0.36)
C1	V1-G	P1s,P2s	0.34 (0.23,0.42)	C2 - C0	0.10 (0.04,0.14)
C2	V1-G	LM-G,P1s	0.72 (0.65,0.80)	C3 - C0	0.02 (0.00,0.07)
C3	V1-G	LM-G,P2s	0.65 (0.56,0.72)	C4 - C1	0.39 (0.31,0.49)
C4	V1-G	LM-G,,P1s,P2s	0.74 (0.67,0.82)	C4 - C0	0.11 (0.07,0.16)

Model	Y	X	R^2	Difference	R^2
D0	AL-G	LM-G	0.73 (0.68,0.78)	D1 - D0	0.01 (-0.06,0.11)
D1	AL-G	P1s, P2s	0.72 (0.64,0.77)	D2 - D0	0.07 (0.04,0.13)
D2	AL-G	LM-G,P1s	0.81 (0.77,0.85)	D3 - D0	0.07 (0.02,0.12)
D3	AL-G	LM-G,P2s	0.80 (0.76,0.83)	D4 - D1	0.13 (0.08,0.19)
D4	AL-G	LM-G,P1s,P2s	0.85 (0.81,0.88)	D4 - D0	0.12 (0.07,0.17)

Table S2: **Regression analysis**

The regression analysis studies the contribution of some features to predicting other features. 144
The table contains different sets of linear regression models. Tables on the left show the R^2 145
posteriors median and 95% CI in the parentheses (Gelman et al. 2019). Y is the dependent 146
variable and X indicates the explanatory variables. The tables on the right show the posterior 147

of R^2 differences between models. As LM is a putative intermediate region between V1 and AL, we compare how much early features P1 timing, late feature LM-P2 timing and V1-P2 timing explain the variance of AL-P2 timing by running regression analysis. We design 5 scenarios: A0, the independent variable only has V1-P2 timing; A1, the independent variables only have P1 timing; A2, besides P1 timing, it considers V1-P2 timing; A3, besides P1 timing, it adds LM-P2 timing; A4, it contains the timing of P1 and both V1-P2 and LM-P2 timing. See the tables on the first row labeled by A. By comparing A0 and A2, P1 timing adds very limited improvement. By comparing the R^2 of A2, A3 with A1, both V1-P2 and LM-P2 timing explain much more than P1 timing. But LM-P2 timing contributes more than V1-P2 timing does, shown by the comparison between A2 and A3. The improvement from A2 to A4 implies that given V1-P2 timing, LM-P2 timing can still add extra prediction power, but not the other way around (nearly zero improvement from A3 to A4).

We apply similar analysis to AL. 5 models with the select variables. See the tables on the second row labeled by B. The conclusions are similar except that given AL-P2 timing, V1-P2 timing can still make some contribution to predicting LM-P2 timing (shown by the contrast between B4 and B3). This further affirms our hypothesis that LM is an intermediate region between V1 and AL. We also conclude that P2 timing features are more relevant in predicting AL-P2 timing or LM-P2 timing rather than P1 timing features, this may be due to large time lag between P1 and P2.

The last two sets of models labeled by C and D are related to G. We design 5 scenarios: C0, the independent variable only has LM-G; C1, the independent variables include all P1 and P2 timing; C2, besides LM-G, it includes all P1 timing; C3, besides LM-G, it includes all P2 timing; C4, includes LM-G and all P1 and P2 timing. Models labeled by D have similar design. LM-G can predict both V1-G and AL-G very well. One difference between C models and D models is that P1s and P2s together can predict AL-G much better than V1-G, see models C1 and D1 and related model differences. This means AL-G is correlated with activities in a broader regions or types than V1-G. This is probably because AL is a higher-order region.

A1 G	91	96	94	91	95	93	93	95
	A1 P1	95	93	93	93	92	93	90
		A1 P2	91	94	93	93	95	92
			A2 G	87	94	88	94	88
				A2 P1	93	89	93	92
					A2 P2	92	95	91
						A3 G	91	95
							A3 P1	95
								A3 P2

Table S3: **CI coverage** CI coverage ratio percentage of each pair of features correlation. A1, A2, A3 stand for 3 virtual areas. G, P1, P2 stand for Gain, Peak-1, Peak-2.

A1 G	93	96	94	92	96	92	92	95
	A1 P1	95	92	92	93	92	93	94
		A1 P2	89	93	90	89	92	89
			A2 G	88	91	85	92	87
				A2 P1	92	92	92	92
					A2 P2	91	92	88
						A3 G	92	91
							A3 P1	92
								A3 P2

Table S4: **CI coverage** The simulation scenario with mild neuron-to-neuron variance. The table is similar to Table S3.

A1 G	93	96	95	92	95	92	94	95
	A1 P1	95	92	92	92	92	93	91
		A1 P2	89	92	92	92	96	90
			A2 G	89	93	84	95	87
				A2 P1	91	94	92	91
					A2 P2	95	93	90
						A3 G	92	92
							A3 P1	92
								A3 P2

Table S5: **CI coverage** The simulation scenario with large neuron-to-neuron variance. The table is similar to Table S3.

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